

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

nextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Tools Platform

Bruno Fosso

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Tools Platform

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- Facilitate find, access and use of tools
 - Define and promote standards for tools documentation and metadata
 - Define and promote best practice for tools development and maintenance

Tools Platform

Tools Platform

The platform activities are characterized by 4 main tasks:

1. Packaging Containerisation and Deployment
2. Performance benchmarking and technical monitoring
3. Registry of Bioinformatic tools and identifiers
4. Software best practice

17,247
tools

23,748
tools

8,982
tools

7,851
tools

Tools Platform

1. **Biocontainers** to collect single efforts for tools containerisation and platforms federation for sustainability.
2. Central repository to manage containers and deployment
3. User guided development in order to identify solutions best suited for users

OpenEBench represents a common platform and environment for tools benchmarking, and reference datasets **FAIR**ification.

It also is designed to sustain the Open Data, Open Source and Open Science principles.

Tools Platform

Bio.tools is a registry of tools and databases (~28k), community-driven, allowing to rapidly and efficiently browse through the indexed software. It employs persistent identifier ([biotools:biomas](#)) and adopt a controlled tools description ontology (**EDAM**) and syntax (**biotools.Schema**).

Workflow Hub is a domain-agnostic registry for workflows designed around FAIR principles

- To improve software quality sustainability, and documentation.
- Facilitate software findability and usage
- Define 4oSS (4 recommendation for Open Source)
- The **Software Management Plan (SMP)** is designed as a guideline in software development, maintenance and sustainability.

Tools Platform

ELIXIR Tools Ecosystem - ELIXIR Implementation Study 2021-23

Tools Platform

Tools Platform

- Web application
- Command-line tool
- Database portal
- Library
- Command-line tool, Web application
- Web API, Web application, Database portal
- Web service
- Desktop application
- Workflow
- Web application, Command-line tool
- Ontology

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Tools Platform

SDP

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Acquired licensed tools for Genomics, Transcriptomics, Epigenomics, Epitranscriptomics, Metagenomics and Metabolomics data analysis

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Deployment of ELIXIR-IT tools through Galaxy instances to make them accessible to a larger user communities

Tools Platform

Plans for the next 3 years:

- Develop and sustain an ecosystem to facilitate tools findability and usage;
- Promote a model for tools design, deploy, maintenance and sustainability through the adoption of SMPs and standardized ontologies;
- Promote software reproducibility in distributed analysis;
- Strengthen the collaboration with ELIXIR and international scientific communities in the adoption of services provided by the platform (OpenEBench, Bio.tools, SMP, Biocontainers)

Thank you
for the
attention

